

BIOTIC STRESS AND MORPHOGENESIS OF CORK OAK SEEDLINGS: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ACROSS MOTHER TREES

Sabiha BOUCHAOUR-DJABEUR^{1*}, Kheloufi BENABDELI², Djamel ALATOU

1 Department of Forest Resources, Laboratory for Water, Soil and Forest Management - Sustainable Development of the Mountainous Areas in the Region of Tlemcen, Tlemcen University, PO Box 119, 13000, Algeria*

2 Department of Biology, Laboratory for Geo-Environmental and Spatial Development, Mascara University, PO Box 350, 29000, Algeria

3 University of Constantine, Laboratory for the Development and Valorization of Plant Genetic Resources, Algeria

**Corresponding author : Sabiha BOUCHAOUR-DJABEUR*

Submission Date: 28 Sep 2025

Approval Date: 22 Oct 2025

Release Date: 28 Oct 2025

Summary

In the mountainous forests of Hafir and Zariefet, located in northwestern Algeria, a study was conducted to assess the impact of acorn predation by insects on the morphological and physiological behavior of cork oak seedlings. Morphologically mature acorns were individually collected from 17 trees. Another batch was gathered directly from the forest soil of both sites. All acorns were then classified according to their origin and placed into cultivation.

For severely damaged acorns, the reduction in stem height growth is 77%; diameter: 78%; number of sheets: 65%; of the leaf surface: 86% for the leaves of wave 1 (V1) and 89% for (V2). Seedlings grown from acorns at different health states underwent changes in spatiotemporal components. They exhibit endogenous rhythmic growth characterized by a succession of structural units. Each wave of growth is essentially identical to the previous one and the one that follows it.

Weak infestation has almost no effect on the morphogenesis of the young plant, while severely infestation affects it vigorously. Apparent rests double during V2 and V3. Examining the spatial components, the average daily elongation of the cauline axis is reduced and the apparent plastochron decreases in number and size of leaves.

The interaction of defense and resistance mechanisms appears to be important, as they can survive damage caused by insects, but this remains closely linked to acorn's behavior (escape strategy), infestation rate, cotyledonary mass and quality.

Key words: *Quercus suber*, acorns' biotic stress, growth, morphogenesis, escape strategy, North-West Algeria.

1. Introduction

Algeria is one of the Mediterranean countries that has been occupied by the oldest civilizations in the world and one of the spaces where natural resources (fauna, flora and soil) have always been solicited. Indeed, it boasts an incomparable ecological wealth in terms of bioclimate, morphology and flora, reflected in a wide variety of high-quality landscapes and natural environments.

With an area of about 2,4 million km², it is the largest country in Africa in the Arab world and the Mediterranean basin. One of the largest deserts in the world, the Sahara, covers more than 2 million km², representing 84% of the territory.

The regions of northern Algeria where climate and environment conditions allow the development of forest formations occupy 250 000 km² or just over 10% of the total area (FAO, 2001). Bordered to the south by the mountains of the Saharan Atlas and even if the woody production is not very important, the Algerian forest provides many goods and services, often non-market, we must make the most of it.

Out of a forest heritage of 4,7 million hectares (ha), the so-called economic and productive forests cover barely 1,2 million ha (DGF, 2018) following the various aggressions that have considerably reduced its surface area and caused the regression or disappearance of numerous animal and plant species.

Constituting one of the most important riches of Algeria, *Quercus suber L.* in spontaneous state is observed only in the western Mediterranean basin and on the Atlantic coast. It covers approximately 2 000 000 ha, including 1 100 000 ha in Europe: Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, and 900 000 ha in North Africa: Algeria, Morocco and Tunisia. It grows in plains as well as mountains and requires a mild and humid climate (Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2021). It is a species that has always been sought for its bark (cork), used in several industries, for its wood of good calorific value and for its acorns very appreciated by the man, wild and domestic animals. Its socio-economic, ecological and landscape roles are very important and make it particularly attractive throughout the Mediterranean (Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2011).

The Algerian cork oak forest that covered an original area varying, according to the authors, between 429 000 and 480 000 ha (third place after Portugal and Spain), are currently estimated at 230 000 ha (DGF 2018) where more than half are old cork oak forest (futaies in french). The large mass of the best and vast forestation is found in the east of the country, mainly in humid and sub-humid areas. Outside this region, the cork oak grows in a rather discontinuous manner as isolated and less important massifs. In the West, it is less frequent; it occurs in Relizane (Ami Moussa), south of Mascara (Nesmoth), near Tiaret (Tagdempt), in the vicinity of Oran (M'sila and Terziza) and especially in Tlemcen (Hafir and Zariefet).

The alarming drop in cork production confirms the difficulties encountered by the species to guarantee permanent production and to regenerate and conserve. This reality is a consequence of the various catastrophic historical events in addition to climate change which has already produced new and more intense disturbance regimes and unforeseeable (Bouchaour-Djabeur, 2016).

These are generally the same issues affecting cork oak forests across the Mediterranean that weaken the cork oak: prolonged droughts, repeated wildfires, regeneration difficulties, poorly adapted management and restoration

programs, inadequate exploitation systems, human activities including domestic animals, diseases, and forest decline.

As a result, the cork oak becomes more vulnerable and suffers significant damage caused by various groups of insects. These pests threaten both its production and regeneration. According to their feeding habits, they can be classified into four categories : defoliators, xylophagous insects, cork depreciators, and acorn pests (Bouchaour-Djabeur, 2016 ; Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2021 ; 2024).

Seed depredation is indeed a major problem. Acorns are often the target of various predators, such as rodents and some insects, which can seriously affect the natural regeneration of these trees. Since natural regeneration is very random and heterogeneous, artificial regeneration based on acorns could be an alternative to address the deficit in recruitment population. Only, the factors influencing the regeneration of oak-The number of different types of cork is high and complex, and the relative intensity of each varies from country to country and region to region within the same country (Bouchaour-Djabeur, 2016).

The Hafir-Zariefet forests, located in Tlemcen in northwestern Algeria, are renowned for their cork production. Since the precolonial period, they have sparked the curiosity and passion of many authors. This interest is explained, first, by the fact that they form the only continuous forest massif in the Oran-Algerian region—despite their limited size and geographic isolation from other cork oak forests that benefit from more favorable climatic conditions. Then, these forests now survive only as relic and isolated stands. In the past, they were much more extensive and, according to Boudy (1955), “offered a better quality of cork.”

These forests are under significant pressure, both anthropogenic and climatic. According to Messaoudene (2008), these pressures are worsening due to the absence of a forest policy specifically aimed at sustainable development. In response to growing concern over the decline of forest heritage, a collective awareness has emerged, leading to new global orientations. These orientations aim to preserve biodiversity and ensure the sustainable development of ecosystems. In this context, « the ecological value of tree species is now considered a priority over their economic value » (Dahmani, 1997).

However, in order to manage and develop sustainably, it is essential to have a thorough understanding of all ecosystem components. It is within this perspective of preservation that our study was conducted, focusing on the consequences of acorn infestation by insects on the morphological and physiological behavior of cork oak seedlings.

The study is divided into two main areas :

1. changes related to morphological parameters (stem height, collar diameter, number of leaves, and leaf area), and
2. changes related to spatio-temporal expression (elongation duration, apparent dormancy, and heteroblasty).

To our knowledge, the effect of biotic stress on cork oak morphogenesis has never been addressed in Algeria. This is why we encountered difficulties in discussing our results.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

To the southwest of the town of Tlemcen on Sequanian sandstones at the northern level of the mountains is a grouping comprising the two interesting cork oak massifs of Zariefet (962 km²) and Hafir (9 872 km²) (PNT, 2000) (Fig. 1). They enjoy a subhumid bioclimat, from 500 to 650 millimeters per year (mm/year). The landscape is very rugged where all the exhibits are present. The dominant slopes range from 12 to 50%. Small areas of bare, rocky terrain are found on the summits and ridge lines. The massif's altitude varies from 700 to 1418 metres (m). The maximum annual average temperature is 18,9°C, the minimum annual average temperature is 8,2°C. "The sandstones have given rise to brown forest soils with a sandy-loam texture, often evolving towards fersiallitic soils" (Gaouar, 1998).

The massif is composed mainly of hardwood trees such as oaks (*Quercus suber*, *Quercus rotundifolia* and *Quercus faginea ssp. tlemceniensis*), *Olea europea ssp. oleaster* and a few feet of *Fraxinus oxyphylla*, but also softwood trees such as *Tetraclinis articulata*, *Juniperus oxycedrus*, *Pinus halepensis*, *Pinus pinaster*, *Cupressus communis* and the Eucalyptus trees in some degraded cantons (they were introduced there). In good resorts, cork oak is mixed with zeen oak (*Quercus faginea*) and holm oak (*Quercus rotundifolia*).

The cork oak forest is very irregular, heterogeneous and unregenerated, it ages with subjects more than two centuries old of which some are unhealthy and testify to great mutilation (Bouchaour-Djabeur, 2001 and 2016 ; Bouhraoua, 2003). Most of it is now transformed into a degraded landscape (density < 100 stems/ha) with the extension of maquis, very dense in *Cistus ladaniferus*, *Cistus salviaefolius*, *Cistus monspeliensis*, *Erica arborea*, *Calicotum*, etc. which sometimes cover the entire soil.

This state of degradation exposes it to a gradual decline and rapid loss of resources (Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2024). It is linked on the one hand to the harsh climatic conditions, aggravated in recent decades by global warming, violent and successive fires especially at Zariefet, the action of pests and human action, and on the other hand, to the physiological state of the strains and the absence of natural regeneration even if it may be more or less acceptable in some places.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the Hafir-Zariefet forest

2.2. Plant material

Ten circular plots (P) from 7 to 20 ares (depending on the density of the stand) were set up, 5 in the forest of Hafir (H) and 5 others in that of Zariefet (Z) (Fig. 2). At the level of each plot, 5 trees (T) were chosen and numbered by the method of Mueller-Dembois and Ellenberg (1974). However, when the stem is composed of several sprigs of coppice, we have retained only the largest sprig, and if they are of the same size, one sprig is selected randomly.

Acorns were harvested from 17 cork oaks out of the 50 subjects that were identified and studied (Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2020; 2021; 2024) (the others did not bear fruit). In each plot, and depending on the importance of acorns production, fresh morphologically ripe acorns were randomly collected according to two modes. The first is traditional, collecting of acorns falling on the ground. The second requires that the acorns do not touch the ground and are picked directly from the trees or by beating with a bed-sheet on the ground.

Figure 2 . Distribution of study plots in Hafir and Zariefet forests (H: Hafir – Z: Zariefet)

2.3. Cultivation

The experiment took place in a nursery with the same altitudinal and climatic provisions as the forests of origin of the acorns and with semi-controlled conditions (shading + watering). The irrigation water comes from an existing well there and is analyzed to see if it is suitable for the production of the plants.

The acorn culture substrate comes from experimental plots of the Hafir and Zariefet cork oak forest. The soil taken from a layer 20 to 60 cm deep was dried and homogenized. Grain size and pH analysis of a soil sample from four horizons revealed a sandy-silty-clay surface texture with a sandy depth (71-89% sand, 6-16% silt, 3-10% clay). The average pH is 7,4.

Acorns harvested from trees (17 trees) and collected from the ground (Hafir and Zariefet) were cleaned and wiped. 30 acorns per quality (3) and per lot (19) are planted (total N = 1710 acorns) (Tab. 1) according to an external examination (Weckerly et al., 1989; Branco et al., 2002; Xiao et al., 2003; Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2011) and a classification according to the following meanings:

1. Healthy Acorns (H): with no bite,
2. Slightly damaged Acorns (S) : detected by adult weevil bites but no larval exit holes, they may still contain insect eggs or young larvae (Fig. 3A),
3. and Severely damaged Acorns (Sd): most with damaged embryos or more than 50% of cotyledons attacked or detected by the presence of mature larvae or exit holes (Fig. 3B; Fig. 3C for *Curculio elephas*) and (Fig. 3D; Fig. 3E for *Cydia fagiglandana*).

Table 1. Criteria and layout of seedlings (T6 to T24: acorns from Hafir Trees, T31 to T47: acorns from Zariefet trees, HS: acorns from Hafir soil, ZS: Acorns from Zariefet soil)

Block 1(arbres)	Number	State of the acorns
Acorns of the tree n°6 (T6H)	30	Healthy acorns (H)
Acorns of the tree n°6 (T6S)	30	Slightly damaged acorns (S)
Acorns of the tree n°6 (T6Sd)	30	Severely damaged acorns (Sd)
.	.	.
.	.	.
.	.	.
Acorns of the tree n°47 (T47H)	30	Healthy acorns
Acorns of the tree n°47 (T47S)	30	Slightly damaged acorns
Acorns of the tree n°47 (T47Sd)	30	Severely damaged acorns
Block 2 (Soil)		
Hafir soil acorns (HSH)	30	Healthy acorns
Hafir soil acorns (HSS)	30	Slightly damaged acorns
Hafir soil acorns (HSSd)	30	Severely damaged acorns
.	.	.
.	.	.
Zariefet Soil acorns (ZSSd)	30	Severely damaged acorns

Figure 3. Cork oak acorns Slightly (S) and Severely damaged (Sd)

A: Slightly damaged Acorns (S)

B, C : Severely damaged Acorns (Sd) for *Curculio elephas*

D, E :Severely damaged Acorns (Sd) for *Cydia fagiglandana*.

2.4. Rearing system and management

The perforated plastic bags on the sides and without bottoms are filled with $\frac{3}{4}$ of substrate and arranged in openwork crates also at the base and on the sides. All the crates are placed on raised boards 20 cm from the ground that we have built and installed in a semi-shaded greenhouse. This outside-ground technique «makes it possible to produce plants without crippling root deformations» (Harfouche, 2003). The acorns are then transplanted horizontally and covered with a layer of potting soil of 2 to 3 cm. This approach with bottomless bags, openwork-based crates and the raised frames cause self-wrapping of roots, but also prevent soil contamination and/or pest attack (Fig. 4).

Manual weeding was undertaken as necessary. Watering is manual two to three times a week, depending on the temperature and regularly controlling the humidity of the substrate.

Figure 4 . Cultivation, system and management of cork oak seedlings

2.5. Seedling Emergence (Bouchaour-Djabeur et al., 2024)

After almost three months of sowing, we noticed the first seedling appear. “An acorn is considered germinated when the radicle pierces the envelopes and manifests its positive geotropism” (Merouani et al., 2001). Germination capacity is the maximum germination rate obtained under the conditions we have chosen. After ten days of germination onset, we followed the germination rate periodically (every 10 days) for ten weeks. The germination rate (GR) is calculated by the following formula (Eq.1) (Maziliak, 1982):

$$GR\% = \frac{\text{Number of sprouted seeds}}{\text{Total number of seeds}} \text{ (Eq.1)}$$

2.6. Seedling growth

The effect of the genotype (individual producer) and the state of health of the acorns were regularly monitored by measurements of growth parameters every two days as soon as the first seedlings appeared. The descriptors considered are:

1. The height (Hei) growth of the stem measured from the collar to the apex.
2. The diameter (D) at the collar is the best predictor of plant vigor according to Mexal and Landis (1990).
3. The number of leaves (LN) is considered a good indicator of the assimilative capacity of the plant and its biomass production (Fiscchesser et Dupuis-Tate, 1996).

4. The leaf area (LA), determined at the end of the experiment on all the leaves of the first and second growth wave by a planimeter type HAAF 017.

2.7. Plant morphogenesis

The periodicity of measurements, taken every two days, allowed us to follow the rhythmic growth of the plants and to determine the spatio-temporal components according to Alatou (1990):

1. The temporal components: are the durations in days of the phases of stem elongation growth and the apical bud rest.
2. Spatial components or heteroblasty: are the number of foliar sets formed per unit of time or rhythm of leaf release (apparent plastochrone) and the morphogenesis of these sets which are in number three:
 - Foliar sets with scaly stipules: are the scales themselves (Sca), the first foliar pieces developed on the caulinaraxis during the formation of a stage. They do not develop.
 - Foliar sets with stipulated assimilator limb: are the actual leaves (Leave) of the plant.
 - Foliar sets with aborted limb stipulated: abortion of the small (1- to 4-mm) limb is early (Lab). These leaf groups surround the scaly bud at the end of a growth wave.
3. Caulinar elongation and leaf growth: is the daily evolution of caulinar axis elongation (mm/day) and apparent plastochrone (number of leaves/day).

2.8. Data Analysis

The various parameters studied were treated by descriptive or comparative statistics in a one-factor analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a Tukey test at the 5% threshold to test for significant differences between the various parameters, and similarly two-input ANOVA. Values of p-value ≤ 0.05 are considered statistically significant. The software used is "Minitab 16".

3. Results

3.1. Seedling growth

3.1.1. Height Growth

The growth in height of the stem is very important for seedlings from healthy and slightly damaged acorns. They follow almost the same trend, with a slight positive difference for healthy acorn seedlings. Although maximum height is recorded in T22 for healthy (>300mm), more than 66% of this category did not germinate. The acorns (Ft) are characterized by a certain heterogeneity, those of T23 and T35 stabilize at 70 mm and 80 mm respectively (Fig. 5). Single-factor ANOVA (based on health status) reveals an extremely significant difference and the Tukey test classifies height growth into 3 groups: A (187,9 mm) for healthy; B (149,1 mm) for slightly damaged; and C (12,1 mm) for those with severely damage (Tab. 2).

Figure 5: Height growth of seedlings from healthy (H), slightly damaged (S) and severely damaged (Sd) acorns

Table 2: One-way ANOVA of total seedling height as a function of acorns health status

Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	p-value
Model	2	9719519	4859760	384,79	0,000***
Error	1707	21558576	12630		
Total corrected	1709	31278095			
Modality	Estimated mean	Groups			
1	187,9	A			
2	149,1	B			
3	12,1	C			

A two-way ANOVA of total height (HT mm) as a function of provenance and health status shows a highly significant difference for provenance and health status, and the same for their interaction (Tab. 3).

Table 3: Two-way ANOVA of total seedling height HT (mm) as a function of provenance and acorns health status

Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	p-value
Provenances	18	2832746	157375	16,46	0,000 ***
State of health	2	9719519	4859760	508,39	0,000 ***
Interaction	36	2924598	81239	8,50	0,000 ***
Error	1653	15801232	9559		
Total	1709	31278095			

3.1.2. Diameter growth at collar

The Diameter growth at collar evolves almost in the same way as that of the height. All seedlings from healthy acorns reach 6 mm in diameter. The seedlings of the severely damaged acorns (Sd) of trees T21, T22, T23 and A24 reach 4 mm at the end of the experiment, whereas those of HSOIL, ZSOIL and T35 approach 3 mm (Fig. 6).

The variance analysis shows a very significant difference between the three states (Tab. 4). However, the Tukey test does not distinguish between individuals of seedlings from (H) and (S) by assigning them group A (5,435 mm – 4,847 mm). Group B contains seedlings from severely damaged acorns with the smallest diameter (1,17 mm).

Figure 6: Diameter growth at collar of seedlings from healthy acorns (H), slightly damaged (S) and severely damaged (Sd)

Table 4: One-way ANOVA of seedling collar diameter (D mm) as a function of acorns health status

Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	P-value
Model	2	181,62	90,81	52,30	0,000***
Error	48	83,34	1,74		
Total corrected	50	264,95			
Modality	Estimated mean	Groups			
1	5,435	A			
2	4,847	A			
3	1,171	B			

3.1.3. Leaves Number

The leaves number of is a good indicator of good water and mineral supply and good biomass production (Dupuitate 1996). The leaves of seedlings from healthy and slightly damaged acorns begin to be discovered in the second week. While those from severely damaged acorns, take much longer and begin to appear in the seventh week.

As soon as the first leaves appear, the number increases with time, reaching more than 25 sheets for healthy (T19, T21, T31) and more than 20 sheets for slightly damaged (T6, T8, T32). The leaves of the seedlings from the acorns (Sd) record the minimum number of leaves. It increases to 9 leaves for T22 and T23. HSOL’s ones reach 8 leaves, then relapse to 4 until the end of the experiment (Fig. 7). The ANOVA at one factor confirms these divergences. The difference between health states is extremely significant (Tab. 5). Grouping with the Tukey method shows 2 groups.

Figure 7: Leaves Number of seedlings from healthy acorns (H), slightly damaged (S) and severely damaged (Sd)

Table 5: One-way ANOVA of seedling leaves number (LN) as a function acorns health status

Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	P-value
Model	2	3616,2	1808,1	97,80	0,000***
Error	54	998,3	18,5		
Total Corrected	56	4614,5			
Modality	Estimated mean	Groups			
1	20,642	A			
2	18,011	A			
3	2,584	B			

3.1.4. Leaf area

The slightly damaged health state slightly reduced the leaf area of both waves W1 and W2 (Fig. 8), the reduction rates are 18% and 21%, respectively. Whereas for the heavily damaged condition, the reduction rate increases strongly, 86% and 89% respectively (Fig. 9). The variance analysis at a controlled factor indicates an extremely significant difference between states for both waves (Tab. 6).

Figure 8: Mean leaf area (MLA) (mm²) per wave and health status of seedlings from healthy (H), slightly damaged (S) and severely damaged (Sd) acorns

Table 6: One-way ANOVA of wave 1 (W1 mm²) and wave 2 (W2 mm²) leaf area of seedlings as a function of acorns health status

W1 (mm ²)					
Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	p-value
Model	2	10777375	5388688	41,06	0,000***
Error	54	7087121	131243		
Total corrected	56	17864496			
W2 (mm ²)					
Source	df	Sum of squares	MS	F	p-value
Model	2	6932145	3466072	032,30	0,000***
Error	54	5794720	107310		
Total corrected	56	12726865			

Figure 9: Leaf area per growth wave (W1 and W2) of seedling leaves from healthy (H), slightly damaged (S) and severely damaged (Sd) acorns

3.2. Plant morphogenesis (Caulinar elongation, apparent rest, leaf growth and heteroblasty)

Cork oak seedlings from acorns with different health states and from various producers, grown in semi-controlled conditions, have undergone changes in the spatio-temporal components. They show a rhythmic growth characterized by an “uninterrupted succession of structural units corresponding to the waves of growth” (Alatou, 1990). These waves are also called shoots, floors or flushes. Each growth wave is substantially identical to the previous and subsequent one (Fig. 10 and Fig. 11).

Figure 10: Young cork oak plant with 2 growth waves

Figure 11: Duration in days of caulinar elongation and apparent rest phases of cork oak seedlings as a function of acorns health status

This rhythmic growth of stems reveals four distinct growth waves. The first begins timidly for healthy (H) and slightly damaged (S) stems, and becomes rapid during March and early April, whatever their origin (harvested from trees or picked up from the ground). The second wave resumes rigorously in May. This is followed by a third wave of weak or slow growth, and finally a fourth wave towards the end of July.

For all seedlings grown from healthy acorns, a growth wave lasts an average of 5 to 7 weeks, divided respectively into a caulinar elongation phase lasting 3 to 4 weeks and an apparent rest phase of the apical bud lasting 2 to 3

weeks. The duration of caulinar elongation decreases for the last three waves, while the rest periods remain identical to those of the first wave (Tab. 7).

The foliar sets with assimilator limb number gradually decreases from one growth wave to the next and heteroblasty remains low and marked by a reduced number of scales and aborted limbs (1 to 2) (Tab. 7). These assimilator limbs are generally of normal size (40 to 50 mm), separated by numerous internodes (In) more or less elongated (8,34 mm on average), up to 25 mm for wave 2 (Fig. 12A). We report exceptional cases where a plant from healthy acorn only records 1 or 2 growth waves (Fig. 12B ; Fig. 12C).

Table 7: Average duration of caulinar elongation, apparent apical bud rest (days) and foliar sets of cork oak seedlings as a function of acorns health status

Acorns Health status	Growth waves	Caulinar elongation (days)	Apparent rest (days)	Scales	Limbs assimilators	Aborted limbs
Healthy (H)	1	30,63 ± 8,03	22,73 ± 5,75	1,67±0,58	13,00±5,57	1,33±0,58
	2	19,82 ± 6,56	22,42 ± 7,90	1,33±0,58	9,00±3,00	1,33±1,15
	3	21,52 ± 6,32	21,72 ± 6,58	1,33±0,58	7,67±1,15	1,00±1,00
	4	19,23 ± 5,30	13,38 ± 6,31	1,67±0,58	4,67±2,08	1,33±1,15
Slightly damaged (S)	1	33,45 ± 3,92	23,28 ± 2,42	2,33±1,53	10,67±2,89	0,67±0,58
	2	19,73 ± 3,79	22,06 ± 5,80	1,33±0,58	6,33±3,21	0,00±0,00
	3	21,92 ± 3,54	23,12 ± 8,72	1,00±1,00	4,67±1,53	1,33±0,58
	4	19,17 ± 6,23	12,01 ± 6,51	0,67±0,58	2,67±0,58	0,67±0,58
Severely damaged (Sd)	1	27,34 ± 14,74	24,83 ± 13,85	2,33±0,58	3,00±1,00	1,00±1,00
	2	23,08 ± 12,62	45,04 ± 31,98	1,33±0,58	2,67±0,58	1,00±1,00
	3	21,80 ± 10,36	34,25 ± 17,55	1,00±1,00	2,00±1,00	0,67±0,58
	4	15,2 ± 6,19	8,5 ± 3,70	1,00±1,00	1,67±0,58	0,67±0,58

The average daily elongation of the caulinar axis remains relatively low, less than 4 mm per two days (Tab. 8). The maximums are observed in the fifth week for W1 (8,22 mm), on the 10th day for W2 (5,18 mm) and on the 16th day for W3 (6,26 mm). They follow almost the same evolution as that of the apparent plastochrone: the eighth week (0,83 F/2 days) for W1 and from the 16th to the 18th day (0,92 F/2 days) for W2.

Table 8: Average values for caulinar elongation (mm/2days) and apparent plastochrone (Leaves/2days) as a function of acorns health status

Acorns Health status	Growth wave	Mean of caulinar elongation (mm/2 days)	Mean of apparent plastochrone (Leaves/2 days)
H	W1	2,514±1,148	0,269±0,244
	W2	3,078±1,492	0,329±0,250
	W3	2,920±1,843	0,147±0,080
	W4	2,415±1,152	0,224±0,099
S	W1	2,747±1,561	0,254±0,209
	W2	3,058±1,340	0,315±0,193
	W3	2,902±1,483	0,165±0,172
	W4	2,116±1,114	0,125±0,067
Sd	W1	0,552±0,406	0,065±0,084
	W2	0,849±0,474	0,017±0,087
	W3	0,552±0,172	0,011±0,019
	W4	0,386±0,136	0,009±0,036

Figure 12: Growth of cork oak plants from a healthy glans (H) where each structural unit is composed in the same way. The diagram shows the length of assimilator limbs (leaves in mm), the nature and number of leaf sets (right), the length of the internodes (mm) according to their rank on the stem (left)

(A): plant from a healthy acorn (H) having built 4 growth waves

(B): plant from a healthy acorn (H) having only 2 waves, but with growth comparable to that of other seedlings with 4 waves of growth.

(C): plant from a healthy glans (H) (A6) having produced 1 wave of growth and recording an evident irregularity regarding the emission of leaves, their lengths and the elongation of the internodes.

In the case of seedlings from slightly damaged acorns, apart from wave 1, which shows a slightly longer caulinar elongation than healthy seedlings, the other three waves show cauline elongation and apparent rest phases

virtually identical to those of healthy seedlings. The number of assimilating limbs decreases on average from one growth wave to the next, and similarly for healthy plants (Tab. 8) (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Growth of cork oak plant from a slightly damaged glans (S) where each structural unit is composed in the same way. The diagram shows the length of assimilator limbs (leaves in mm), the nature and number of leaf sets (right), the length of the internodes (mm) according to their rank on the stem (left). The plant has built 4 growth waves, the number of leaves high in V2 and remains relatively stable in V3, dimensions are also important.

For the seedlings from the severely damaged acorns, caulinar elongation times decreased for the first wave ($27,34 \pm 14,74$), increased for the second wave ($23,08 \pm 12,62$) and remained stable for the third wave ($21,80 \pm 10,36$) (Tab. 7). The apparent rest of W1 slightly increases compared to healthy, and doubles for W2 and W3, reaching $45,04 \pm 31,98$ and $34,25 \pm 17,55$ respectively. The apparent plastochrone is increasingly smaller than that of healthy (Tab. 7). Leaves are no more than 30 mm long in V2 and 21 mm in V3 and V4 (Fig. 14A).

The average daily elongation of the caulinar axis decreases considerably than that of healthy patients, it reaches its maximum at the fourth week for W1 (2,05 mm). The apparent plastochrone is also very low, it reaches 0,25 L/2days at the sixth week for W1 and 0,14 L/2days at the 16th day for W2 (14B).

Figure 14: Growth of cork oak plant from a strongly damaged gland (Sd) in successive waves, where each structural unit is composed in the same way. The diagram shows the length of assimilator limbs (leaves in mm), the nature and number of leaf sets (right), the length of the internodes (mm) according to their rank on the stem (left).

(A): plant from a strongly damaged acorn (Sd) having built 4 growth waves

(B): plant from a strongly damaged glans (Sd) having built 2 waves with a relatively stable number of leaves and lack of link between the length of the leaf and the length of the internodes.

Conclusion

Seedlings that built one to four waves of growth vary greatly from one tree to another (or from those harvested from the ground), depending on the health of the acorn and within the same health. All seedlings from acorns (H) or (S) easily built four waves of growth. The proportion is respectively 100% of (H) for T9 and 76% of (S) for T21. Particularly for seedlings from acorns from trees T21 and T22, the (Sd) built four waves of growth with respectively 7% and 34%. Those from tree T35 (Zariefet) also show an exception, in particular 50% of the (H) seedlings took longer to reach the end of the experiment at the third wave of growth only, while 40% of the (Sd) managed to build 4 waves of growth (Fig. 15).

Figure 15: Proportion of seedlings having built n growth waves

The height growth in successive waves shows an extremely significant difference for seedlings from healthy and slightly damaged acorns, and a low significance for the heavily damaged ones. However, for (S) and (Sd), the Tukey test does not see any difference in growth between waves 2 and 3 (Tab. 9).

Table 9: Summary One-way ANOVA of the height (H mm of seedlings from healthy, slightly and severely damaged acorns) as a function of the Waves

Acorns Health status	p-value	W1	W2	W3	W4
H	0,000***	90,96 A	70,42 B	52,39 BC	36,78 C
S	0,000***	94,18A	68,41 B	55,43 B	37,29 C
Sd	0,020*	34,34 A	26,79 AB	10,78 AB	4,81 B

4. Discussion

4.1. Seedlings growth

The quality of a plant is the result of many morphological and physiological characteristics that control its development and growth potential (Aussenac et al., 1988). Growth in stem height, collar diameter and leaves number also depend on the physiological integrity of the almond, the mass and quality of the cotyledons and the infestation intensity. Growth of severely damaged seedlings is slowed down only in the first weeks after germination. Respectively for healthy, slightly and severely damaged: the height of growth varies between 250 - > 300 mm; 180 - 300 mm; 70 - 270 mm; diameter ranges from 5 – 6,6 mm; 5 – 6; 2 - 4. Number of leaves is 23 - >25; 15 – 23; 5 - 9. Morphologically, stem height and collar diameter growth remain within the standards cited by Lamhamdi (1997) who states that a good forest plant should reach a target of 200 to 250 mm high and 3 to 4 mm in diameter.

Regarding the leaf surface, it is slightly reduced for both waves W1 and W2 with rates of 18% and 21% respectively for the slightly damaged. For the severely damaged, the reduction rate increases strongly to 86% and 89%, respectively. Depredation seems to contribute to the decrease in photosynthetic activity.

Our results showed that insect depredation of acorns considerably reduced the growth rate of seedlings, depending on the intensity of infestation. Stem height growth was reduced by 77%; diameter by 78%; number of leaves by 62-65%; leaf area by 86% for wave 1 leaves and 89% for wave 2 leaves. These results are perfectly comparable with other studies on oaks (Oliver and Chapin, 1984; Fukumoto and Kajimura, 2000; Branco et al, 2002). According to Bouchaour-Djabeur et al, (2011), cotyledonary damage affects the susceptibility of acorns and resulting cork oak seedlings and may well be the main factor in subsequent mortality.

4.2. Caulinar elongation, apparent rest, leaf growth and heteroplasty

Biological rhythms are highly diverse (Millet, 1987). Depending on species and climate, the succession of floors of clearly distinct ramifications underlines the existence of a rhythmic activity of growth (Crabbé, 1993).

For a seedling from a healthy glans, these structural units or growth waves cover a caulinar elongation phase of 3 to 4 weeks and an apparent rest phase of the apical bud of 2 to 3 weeks. The rest is only apparent, because foliar primordia (embryonic structures of leaves) are formed without stopping (Alatout, 1990). The length of caulinar elongation decreases little for the last three waves, while the rest periods remain identical to those of the first wave.

About spatial components, the number of foliar sets with assimilator limb decreases progressively from one growth wave to the next. Heteroblasty remains low, marked by a reduced number of scales and aborted limbs (0 to 3). These assimilator limbs are generally of normal size (40 to 50 mm), separated by numerous, moderately long internodes.

«For the morphologist, on one axis, it is often thanks to the presence of long and short internodes that the plant has the ability to grow in a rhythmic way» (Alatou, 1990). We find that the rhythmic growth of the control is well marked and approximately identical to that described by Alatou (1990) at 12°C J.L. (Luminous Day) (16 h/ 24 h) during the first two waves:

- The times of elongation are approximately comparable to those of apparent rest.
- The internodes are quite long, associated with medium-sized leaves as well.
- The reduction in sheet length goes hand in hand with the reduction in internode length.
- The apparent plastochrone is irregular.
- The elongation speeds of the stem are not necessarily in phase opposition with those of extension of the leaves, one is not at the expense of the other, caulinar stop always precedes the stop of growth of the leaves. However, this is not so marked for pedunculate oak and zeen oak (Alatou, 1990).

Cork oak therefore shows a weak but regular capacity for internode elongation, associated with a similarly regular organogenesis that allows development to be directed towards prolonged growth. With a few exceptions, stem elongation is related to leaf emission, which is more active when stem elongation is more intense and decreases when caulinar growth slows down (Maillard et al., 1987).

The transition from one stage to another is still marked by one or two small leaves associated with shorter internodes, and a reduced number of scales (0 to 3). On the morphological level, there is a link between leaf length and internode length in both healthy and slightly damaged seedlings. According to Maillard et al. (1987), this relationship between leaf length and internode length in *Terminalia superba* is not general; in the common Mandarin tree, leaf length varies randomly. According to the same authors, the leaves exert a stimulating influence on internode growth; thus, they exert an early regulatory role on cell division and therefore on the future growth of the internodes.

Concerning the temporal components, the durations of the caulinar elongation phases are heterogeneous, much more from one growth wave to another than from one health state to another. If the latter are relatively identical, apparent rests, on the other hand, show an increase for (Sd), particularly doubling during W2 and W3.

Regarding the spatial components, the size of the leaves does not exceed 30 mm in length in W2 and remains less than 30 mm in length in W3 and W4. The heteroblasty is also low. The average daily elongation of the caulinar axis decreases considerably from that of healthy. The apparent plastochrone is increasingly reduced compared with that of healthy individuals, which show the following reduction rates:

- W1: 23% for (S) and 76% for (Sd)
- W2: 33% for (S) and 66% for (Sd)
- W3: 42% for (S) and 71% for (Sd)
- W4: 50% for (S) and 58% for (Sd)

5. Conclusion

Cork oak seedlings from acorns with different health states and from various producers, grown in semi-controlled conditions, have undergone changes in the spatio-temporal components. They exhibit endogenous rhythmic growth characterized by a succession of identical structural units. Each wave of growth is substantially identical to the previous and subsequent one.

The heavy infestation of acorns has a negative effect on the rhythmic growth of seedlings. A certain disorder is shown, especially for the relationship between the length of the leaf and that of the internode, but also for the emission of the leaves which decreases strongly in W3 as well for the healthy or the slightly damaged ones. Apparent rest increases considerably, notably from single to double during W2 and W3.

Regarding the spatial components, the intensity of the infestation affects the average daily elongation of the caulinar axis (height growth) and the apparent plastochrone (decrease in number and size of leaves).

A complex relationship seems to exist between acorns and insects. Apart from insecticides, other studies of treatments of acorns or producing trees would deserve particular interest, notably, the development of strategies for optimizing natural defenses.

Moreover, specific silviculture is the first measure to be adopted to remedy this situation. And to promote the adaptation and diversity of the species, it is essential that reforestation by natural regeneration be encouraged; and/or by the use of local provenances or possibly by seeds able to adapt to the site.

It is important to remember that regeneration should be monitored by studying the physical and biotic factors responsible, because the recruitment of a species into a plant community is often limited by events occurring

during the early stages of its life. Seed production, germination and the first phase of survival and growth are under the control of numerous abiotic factors. However, these factors are not the only ones acting on the regeneration of a given species, biotic interactions, which include plant-plant interactions as well as plant-organism interactions (predation), are all equally important.

6. Bibliographical references

1. Alatou, D., (1990). Research on the determinism of the rhythmic growth of oak: *Quercus pedunculata Ehrh - Quercus mirbeckii Durieu - Quercus suber L.* - Morphological, biochemical and ecophysiological study. Thesis Doct. D'Etat en Sci. Nat. Univ. Blaise Pascal, Clermont II, France and Univ. Constantine, Inst. of Sci. And nature, Algeria, 109p+Annexes.
2. Aussenac, G., Guehl, J.M., Kaushal, P., Granier, A. and Grieu, P., (1988). Physiological criteria for assessing the quality of forest plants before planting. Rev. For. Fr. special no., 131-149.
3. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S., Benabdeli, K., Bejamaa, M. L., Stiti, B. (2011): Depredation of cork oak acorns by insects and possibilities for germination and seedling growth. – Geo- Eco-Trop 35: 69-80.
4. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S., Benabdeli, K., Taib, N., Bouhraoua, R. T., Mahdjoub, T. (2020): Variability of acorn production of *Quercus suber L.* in the Hafir-Zariefet forest (Tlemcen Mountains, North-West Algeria). – Geo-Eco-Trop 44(3): 487-501.
5. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S., Benabdeli, K., Hadjadj, K., Soufan, W., Taib, N. And Rihan, H. Z. (2024). Biotic stress and physiological behavior of *Quercus Suber* acorns: variability between producers' individuals. Applied Ecology and Environmental Research 22(5):3941-3957.
6. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S., Benabdeli, K., Taib, N. (2021): Cork oak acorns of the Hafir- Zariefet oak cork forest (Tlemcen, Algeria): characteristics, health status and insect infestation. – Geo-Eco-Trop 45(4): 599-615.
7. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S. (2001): Sanitary diagnosis of several cork oak forests in western Algeria. Particular study of the main insect pests. – Magister's thesis, University of Tlemcen, Algeria.
8. Bouchaour-Djabeur, S. (2016): Impact of acorn quality on cork oak regeneration: case of the oranese forests (Algeria). – Doctoral thesis in science, University of Tlemcen, Algeria.
9. Boudy, P., (1955). North African Forest Economy. Volume 4: Forestry Description of Algeria and Tunisia. Larose, Paris, 483p.
10. Bouhraoua, R.T. (2003). Health status of some cork oak forests in western Algeria. Special study of problems posed by insects. Thesis. Doct. Dept. Forest. Fac.Sci.,Univ.Tlemcen, 267p.
11. Branco, M., Branco, C., Merouani, H. and Almeida, M.H., (2002). *Germination success, survival and seedling vigour of Quercus suber acorns in relation to insect damage.* Forest Ecol. Manage. 166, 159-164.
12. Crabbé, J., (1993). The rhythmic growth of trees, basis of their temporal organization. In: Study Group of the Tree, «The growth rate, basis of the temporal organization of the tree», Angers, 1-11. DAHMANI, 1997).

13. DGF, (2018): Forest fires in Algeria: Analysis and prospects. – General Directorate of Forests, Algiers.
14. Fiscchesser, B. and Dupuis-Tate, T. (1996). The Illustrated Guide to Ecology. Ed. Mornings, 319P.
15. FAO (2000). L'étude prospective du secteur forestier en Afrique (FOSA) : Algérie. 60p.
16. Fukumoto, H. and Kajimura, H., (2000). *Effects of insect predation on hypocotyl survival and germination success of mature Quercus variabilis acorns*. J. Forest Res. 5, 31-34.
17. Gaouar, A., (1980). Hypotheses and reflections on the degradation of forest ecosystems in the Tlemcen region (Algeria). For. medit. 2(2), 131-145.
18. Harfouche, A. (2003): Practical guide for the recognition of seed-bearing trees and stands, harvesting, treatment, conservation and the sowing of cork oak acorns in the nursery. – I.N.R.F.
19. Maziliak, P. (1982): Plant physiology growth and development. – Ed. Herman.
20. Merouani, H., Branco, C., Almeida, M.H., Pereira, J.S. (2001): Physiological behavior of cork oak acorns (*Quercus suber* L.) during their conservation and variability between individual producers. – Ann. For. Sci. 58:143-153.
21. Maillard, P., Jacques, M., Miginiac, E. and Jacques, R., (1987). Growth of young *Terminalia superba* under controlled conditions. Ann. Sci. For., 44(1), 67-84.
22. Messaoudene, M., (2008). Cork oak reforestation. Forestry Research Unit, Tizi-Ouzou Regional Station, Report 19 p.
23. Mexal, J.G. and Landis, T.D., (1990). *Target seedling concepts; height and diameter*. Combined Meeting Western Forest Nursery Associations. Rose R., Ed., 13-17.
24. Millet, B., (1987). Rhythms in the plant world. In the development of plants, theoretical and synthetic aspects. Collectioo Theoretical biology 2 by G. Chauvet and H. Le Guyader, Ed. Masson (2), 231-243.
25. Mueller-Dombois, D., Ellenberg, H. (1974): Aims and Methods of Vegetation Ecology. Vegetation Analysis in the Field. – John Wiley and Sons, New York.
26. Oliver, A.D. and Chapin, J.B., (1984). *Curculiofluvus (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) and its effects on acorns of live oaks, Quercus virginiana Miller*. Environ. Entom. 13, 1507-1510.
27. PNT, (2000). TLEMEN NATIONAL PARK. The oak grove of Hafir Tlemcen (Oranie Algeria). National Park Report de Tlemcen, 2000. 7p.
28. Weckerly, F.W., Sugg, D.W., Semlitsch, R.D. (1989): Germination success of acorns (*Quercus*): insect and tannins. – Can. J. Forest Res. 19:811-815.
29. Xiao, Z. S., Wang, Y. S., Zhang, Z. B. (2003): The ability to discriminate weevil- infested nuts by rodents: potential effects on regeneration of nut-bearing plants. – Acta Theriol. Sinica 23: 312-320.